

Spectrophotometric evaluation of leaching behaviour and ground water contamination of anilofos

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Abstract : With a view to evaluate the leaching potential and consequently surface and ground water contamination, the adsorption of anilofos, an organophosphorus herbicide, on five soils of different characteristics has been studied using a batch equilibrium technique. A spectrophotometric methodology based on the reaction of methyl mercaptan, formed from microwave assisted alkaline hydrolysis of anilofos with carbon disulphide and nickel(II) acetate to form methyl isobutyl ketone extractable yellow nickel(II) methyl thioxanthate complex showing λ_{\max} at 378 nm has been developed for the purpose. The leaching potential evaluated in terms of ground water ubiquity score (GUS) has values in the range 0.76–0.97 thus classifying it as non-leacher herbicide. If used in recommended dose, it does not represent hazard to ground water contamination.

Keywords : Anilofos, spectrophotometry, leaching, GUS.

Introduction

The use of pesticides has certainly increased agricultural production but there are some potential hazards and risks associated with their use. These effects of pesticide use usually stem from a lack of understanding of the impact of these chemicals on the environment and are compounded by their indiscriminate and overuse. The use of these chemicals has resulted in pollution of soil and water due to their leaching and migration to water sources. Soil is the ultimate reservoir for these chemicals irrespective of their application target. The pesticides get fractionated between soil solution phase (free form) and soil solid phase through adsorption on clay and organic fractions (bound form)¹. The applied pesticide adsorbed by soil constituents is desorbed in relation to change in the concentration of soil constituents and hence undesirable side effects results due to contamination of the environment and phytotoxicity to the subsequent crops. Adsorption of pesticides is a natural phenomenon which influences the extent of surface and ground water contamination. The movement of water through soil is the principal mechanism for the pesticide to reach water bodies

and it is unadsorbed fraction (free form) of the pesticide which contaminates surface and ground water². Hence, the understanding of the adsorption process that controls the penetration of a pesticide into water bodies is of great importance to environmental regulation and pollution control.

Anilofos-[(S-4-chlorophenyl-N-isopropylcarbaniloyl-methyl)]-O,O-dimethyl phosphorodithioate is a pre-emergence and early post-emergence selective herbicide widely used for the control of various annual grass weeds in rice based cropping system either alone or as a mixed herbicide³⁻⁵. Anilofos is moderately toxic and causes neural and cellular dysfunction, exhibit anticholinesterase activity, induce developmental toxicity and negative effects on the non target organisms and the ecosystem are also reported⁶⁻⁸. It is also reported to cause contamination of surface water and aquatic organisms in rivers and lakes⁶. The frequent detection of pesticides in surface and ground water has led to a number of experimental studies on pesticide adsorption on soils⁹⁻¹¹. This, therefore, prompted us to investigate the leaching behaviour of this herbicide by studying its adsorption on five soils of H.P. region

where this herbicide is maximally used. A new simple, rapid and sensitive extractive spectrophotometric method has been developed for the purpose. The inherent ease and simplicity of spectrophotometric methods coupled with the availability of inexpensive and reliable instruments are important reasons for their popularity. Methods based on HPLC⁹, LC¹², GC¹³⁻¹⁵, enzymatic¹⁶ are also reported in the literature to the determination of this herbicide but high cost of the technique comes in the way of their wide adoption especially by the laboratories of the limited means.

The proposed method is based on the microwave assisted alkaline hydrolysis of the herbicide to form potassium methyl mercaptide and the latter is transformed into MIBK extractable yellow nickel(II) methylthioxanthate through reaction with carbon disulphide and nickel(II) acetate. The analysis is accomplished by measuring the colour of MIBK extract at 378 nm against a reagent blank. The other hydrolytic products and excess of carbon disulphide and nickel(II) acetate do not interfere in the proposed method. Microwave assisted hydrolysis is an effective alternative to conventional procedure as it reduces the time of hydrolysis and problems associated to analyte losses and atmospheric contamination^{17,18}.

That mercaptans react with carbon disulphide in the presence of an alkali to form potassium thioxanthates and the latter form nickel(II) thioxanthates is quite well known^{19,20}.

The method has been successfully applied to the analysis of anilofos in commercial formulations and subsequently validated to study its adsorption on five soils of different characteristics for the purpose of evaluation of its leaching potential and surface and ground water contamination. The adsorption parameters viz. soil adsorption coefficient (K_d), soil organic carbon partition coefficient (K_{oc}), Gibb's free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy change (ΔH°) and entropy change (ΔS°) have been calculated for evaluating the leaching behaviour of the herbicide in terms of ground

water ubiquity score (GUS) to access the hazard to surface and ground water contamination.

Results and discussion

Prompted by the observations that methyl mercaptan formed from microwave assisted alkaline hydrolysis of anilofos react with nickel(II) acetate in the presence of carbon disulphide to form methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK) extractable nickel(II) methyl thioxanthate complex, we have succeeded in developing the proposed extractive spectrophotometric method. Effect of time of hydrolysis and pH on the development, stability and sensitivity of the colour vis-à-vis development of proposed method has been studied before applying it to the analysis of anilofos in commercial formulation and soil adsorption study. The optimum time required for complete hydrolysis in microwave oven corresponds to 60 s. It has also been observed that yellow colour is stable for atleast 120 min. Further extraction of coloured product in MIBK is also complete at this pH which is maintained with the use of sodium acetate-HCl buffer. MIBK has been particularly chosen because it extracts the coloured complex quantitatively from its aqueous solution requiring an equilibrium time of 10 min and is safe in comparison of commonly used

toxic extracting solvents like chloroform, ethyl acetate etc. Thiophosphoric acid and other hydrolytic products and the reagent i.e. nickel(II) acetate are not extractable with MIBK, hence do not interfere in the proposed method. Under the optimized experimental conditions, the proposed spectrophotometric method obeys Beer's law in the range 3.68–73.6 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of anilofos solution. The molar absorptivity (ϵ) and Sandell's sensitivity have been found to be $1.11 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.33 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ at 378 nm. Anilofos in the range 5.52–73.6 μg could be determined with a maximum relative standard deviation (RSD) of 1.08%. The method when applied to the assay of anilofos in its commercial formulations gave recoveries in the range 89.4–97.8% of the nominal content with

RSD's in the range 0.62–1.02% (Table 1). The formulation analysis is essential not only to ensure the quality of its marketed products to the purpose of quality control but also to obtain reliable adsorption data. The results have however, been compared by an independent method²¹. To assess the validity of the proposed method in soil adsorption study, the effect of various common

Table 1. Assay of a commercial formulation containing 30% active ingredient

Active ingredient taken (µg)	Recovery (%)	
	Present method ^a	Comparison method ^b
5.52	90.2 ± 1.02	92.4 ± 0.98
11.04	89.4 ± 0.86	90.2 ± 1.04
16.56	97.8 ± 0.80	88.8 ± 0.92
33.12	96.4 ± 0.88	94.4 ± 0.68
55.20	92.7 ± 0.62	90.6 ± 0.72

^aValues are mean of five determinations with standard deviation (±). ^bReference method²¹.

ions on the determination of this herbicide has been studied. The method has been found to be free from interferences due to Na⁺, K⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Al³⁺, Fe²⁺, Pb²⁺, OAc⁻, PO₄³⁻, NO₃⁻, NO₂⁻, CO₃²⁻, SO₄²⁻, Cl⁻ present in soil.

A number of models are available to evaluate the leaching potential of pesticide and the associated environmental pollution risks in terms of surface and ground water contamination. The ground water ubiquity score (GUS) is the most commonly used model which relates pesticide persistence (half life) and K_{oc} ^{22,23}. The GUS index is determined by using the experimentally observed K_{oc} value for each soil sample type and the reported half life of anilofos¹⁵.

$$GUS = \log(t_{1/2}) [4 - \log(K_{oc})] \quad (1)$$

The proposed spectrophotometric method has been validated to study the adsorption of anilofos at two temperatures viz. 20 °C and 30 °C on five soils where it is maximally used with a view to calculate adsorption parameters viz. K_d , K_{oc} , ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 ²⁴⁻²⁶ as :

$$K_d = X/C_e \quad (2)$$

$$K_{oc} = K_d \times (100\% \text{ OC}) \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta G^0 = -RT \ln K_d \quad (4)$$

where K_{dn} is the apparent equilibrium constant and is given by

$$\ln \{(K_d)_2/(K_d)_1\} = \Delta H^0/R \{(T_2 - T_1)/T_1 T_2\} \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta S^0 = (\Delta H^0 - \Delta G^0)/T \quad (6)$$

where R = gas constant (JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹), T = absolute temperature (K), $t_{1/2}$ = pesticide persistence (half life), OC = organic carbon content of soil.

Adsorption isotherms have been evaluated by using Freundlich's adsorption equation by batch equilibrium technique on five Indian soils. The characteristics of each soil are given in Table 2. An adsorption isotherm is a graph of the equilibrium surface excess or amount of pesticide adsorbed (X , mg kg⁻¹) plotted against the equilib-

Table 2. Characteristics of five soils used in the adsorption study of anilofos

Soil sample	pH	Clay (%)	Organic carbon (%)	Cation Exchange Capacity (meq/100 g)
I	7.43	16.3	0.59	8.80
II	4.94	10.2	0.96	9.23
III	7.49	9.8	1.06	17.59
IV	6.87	12.5	1.32	12.20
V	5.69	26.3	2.20	37.38

rium solution concentration of the pesticide (C_e , mg L⁻¹). The X and C_e have been determined by the proposed method. According to the initial portion of the curve, these isotherms may be classified as L-type of Gile's classification²⁷. The L-type curves indicates a relatively high affinity between the solid surface and solute at the initial stages of the isotherms²⁸ and indicative of a gradual decrease in sites available for sorption as the concentration of the solute in the solution increases²⁹. The adsorption coefficients K_f and n_f were calculated for five soil samples from Freundlich's adsorption equation from the plot of $\log X$ versus $\log C_e$ (Figs. 1, 2) and results are presented in Table 3. The adsorption coefficient K_f represents the amount of pesticide adsorbed at an equilibrium concentration of 1 mg L⁻¹ and n_f represents the variation in adsorption with varying concentration of pesticide². Further, the n_f values less than unity (< 1.0) at 20 °C and 30 °C, indicates a convex or L-type nature of the isotherm, which infer that there is minimum competition from solvent molecules for adsorption sites on the adsorbing surface³⁰. The K_d and K_{oc} of pesticide are basic parameters used to measure the strength of sorption of

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log X$ versus $\log C_e$ for the evaluation of Freundlich's adsorption coefficients K_f and n_f at 20 °C.

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log X$ versus $\log C_e$ for the evaluation of Freundlich's adsorption coefficients K_f and n_f at 30 °C.

Table 3. Adsorption parameters for anilofos on five soils

Soil sample	K_f	n_f	20 °C			30 °C				
			K_d	K_{oc}	GUS	K_d	K_f	n_f	K_{oc}	GUS
I	13.45	0.69	4.79	812.62	0.76	4.01	8.86	0.77	680.32	0.81
II	21.87	0.63	6.34	660.47	0.82	4.90	9.48	0.80	510.08	0.90
III	23.42	0.62	7.31	690.03	0.81	5.77	15.49	0.62	544.50	0.88
IV	26.05	0.61	8.28	627.15	0.84	6.74	17.09	0.71	510.86	0.90
V	30.95	0.62	10.69	485.99	0.92	9.07	28.13	0.61	412.11	0.97

pesticides to soils and are directly related to its mobility and persistence. K_{oc} relates to the hydrophobicity of the

pesticides. Organic matter and clay in the soil participate in the sorption of pesticide in soil³¹⁻³³. Soil with higher

organic and clay content consequently higher K_d and K_{oc} have higher potential to sorb the pesticide. Cation exchange capacity (CEC) and pH of the soil also affect the adsorption of the pesticide in soils. CEC is directly proportional to hydrophobic nature of soil. Greater is the value of CEC of soil, its surface will be more hydrophobic and anilofos being more hydrophobic (low water solubility) thus has higher adsorption affinity for the soils with higher CEC³⁴. The pH of the soil also governs the adsorption of pesticides. In general adsorption of pesticides is less in alkaline than in acidic soils^{32,35}. However, at quite higher and lower pH of the soil, adsorption of pesticides decreases due to change in clay mineralogy or destroying the crystal lattice³⁶. Higher adsorption of anilofos in soil V and soil IV are in good agreement with the above observations (Table 3).

The thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of anilofos on five soils have also been evaluated and are presented in Table 4. The negative value of ΔS° is due to decrease in randomness with adsorption. The values of ΔG° and ΔH° have also been observed negative in all the soil types studied suggesting the energetically favourable

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of anilofos on five soils

Soil samples	ΔG° (kJ mol ⁻¹)		ΔH° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS° (JK mol ⁻¹)
	20 °C	30 °C	25 °C	25 °C
I	-3.82	-3.39	-13.12	-0.0314
II	-4.50	-3.87	-19.02	-0.0490
III	-4.85	-4.27	-17.46	-0.0426
IV	-5.15	-4.65	-15.19	-0.0340
V	-5.77	-5.37	-12.13	-0.0216

adsorption process. From the negative value of ΔH° it can be inferred that the value of soil adsorption coefficients decreased with rise in temperature. This is due to the effect of temperature on the weak binding between anilofos and soil particles³⁷⁻³⁹.

The GUS index for anilofos determined by using experimentally determined K_{oc} values for each soil type and reported half life of anilofos¹⁵, shows values in the range 0.76–0.97, thus classifies it as a non-leacher in terms of classification of pesticides as leacher (GUS > 2.8); transition (2.8 > GUS < 1.8) and non-leacher (GUS < 1.8)²³. Consequently, it does not represent hazard to surface and

ground water contamination. As observed above, the adsorption of pesticide increases in soils of high organic content, soils where this pesticide is used indiscriminately should be amended with additives of high organic matter viz. manure, peat, compost etc. in order to increase their retention and consequently to reduce their mobility.

Experimental

Spectrophotometric measurements were made with Spectronic 200⁺ spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched glass cells. Acetonitrile (Merck) was distilled from phosphorus pentoxide (5 g L⁻¹) and the fraction distilling at 81 °C was collected. Anilofos (93%, Gharda Chemicals Ltd., Mumbai), was used and its purity was however checked by a reported method²¹. A commercial formulation of the herbicide containing 30% active ingredient EC, Nidan (Gujrat Insecticide Ltd.) was procured from local authorised pesticide dealer. The soils from Lahaul Spiti region of Himachal Pradesh were air-dried and passed through 40 mesh sieves to remove stones and large particles. The characteristics of the five soils are summarized in Table 2.

Preparation of calibration graph for pure compound :

Aliquots (0.1–3.0 mL) of standard solution of (10⁻³ mol L⁻¹ in acetonitrile) were taken in 10 mL measuring flasks and volume made to 3 mL with acetonitrile. Each solution was mixed with aqueous potassium hydroxide (1 mL, ~ 1 mol L⁻¹) and 3 mL of distilled water and kept in microwave oven for 60 s. Each hydrolyzed solution was then mixed with one drop (~ 100 μ L) of carbon disulphide (AR, Merck) to form potassium methyl thioxanthate and then treated with 2 mL aqueous acetic acid (~ 1 mol L⁻¹) to neutralize the excess alkali. Each solution was poured into a 100-mL separating funnel containing 1 mL, 0.01 mol L⁻¹ aqueous nickel(II) acetate (CDH, LR) and 10 mL of sodium acetate-HCl buffer (pH ~ 3.0). The contents of the funnel were equilibrated two times with methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK, Merck, AR) using 4 mL each time. The MIBK layer was separated and final volume of the extract was made to 10 mL with MIBK. The extract was dried by shaking with anhydrous sodium sulphate (2 g) and the absorbance of yellow MIBK extract was measured at 378 nm against a reagent and calibration curve was prepared by plotting absorbance values against concentration of pure compound. Beer's law is obeyed in the

range 3.68–73.6 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of anilofos solution. A single large sample of the formulation equivalent to 9.2 mg anilofos was dissolved in 25 mL acetonitrile. Suitable aliquots (0.15–2.0 mL) of acetonitrile extracts of the commercial formulation of anilofos were taken and processed for analysis in the same manner as described above. Assay results are given in Table 1.

Soil adsorption study :

Triplicate soil samples (2 g) were taken in 50 mL conical flasks were equilibrated with 3 mL acetonitrile solution of anilofos in the concentration range from 18.39–110.34 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and 7 mL distilled water. The contents of each flask were stirred to bring effective mixing by shaking mechanically at 150 rpm for 12 h equilibrium time (estimated time required for equilibrium to be reached between anilofos adsorbed and anilofos in solution) and placed in shaker at 20 °C and 30 °C. After 12 h the suspensions were centrifuged and equilibrium concentration (C_e) was determined in the supernatant in the same manner as described above for pure compound. The various adsorption and thermodynamic parameters were calculated by using eqs. (1)–(6) and are given in Tables 3 and 4 respectively.

Conclusion

The applied pesticide ultimately enters soil and then to aquatic environment through leaching resulting into surface and ground water contamination. The risk of contamination depends on the concentration of pesticide in solution phase which in turn depends on its adsorption in soil. The leaching behaviour of anilofos in terms of GUS index which is a measure of surface and ground water contamination has been evaluated based on its adsorption on five soils of different characteristics viz. organic matter, clay content, CEC and pH at two temperatures i.e. 20 °C and 30 °C. From the adsorption study it is concluded that anilofos is adsorbed maximally in soil V followed by IV, III, II and I amongst the five soils studied. But overall, high values of $K_{oc} > 300$ suggest strong adsorption of the insecticide on all five soil types. GUS values in the range 0.76–0.97 classify it as non leacher and does not represent hazard to ground water contamination. However, excessive use of this insecticide can pose a potential threat to the aquatic environment. This contamination risk can be overcome by adjusting applica-

tion dose and amending soil with materials rich in organic carbon content viz. farmyard manure, compost etc. Which will not only reduce its leaching losses but also increase the fertility of the soil. This remedial measure is in consistent with the observed trend of increased adsorption of anilofos in soils with high organic carbon content.

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